

Guarantees Of The Juvenile Accused At The Pre-Trial Stage In Iraqi Law

Muna Asree Hamad

Article Info

Article History

Received:
September 10, 2024

Accepted:
December 11, 2024

Keywords :

Trial, Event, Guarantees,
Investigation

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14392428

Abstract

The pre-trial stage is one of the most serious stages of a criminal case. It is all the more dangerous that it represents the event's first confrontation with public authority. Therefore, the legal rules in the area of juvenile justice have developed a set of recommendations concerning the need to enact juvenile legislation that includes some guarantees at the evidentiary stage and thus provides guarantees for the juvenile accused at the preliminary investigation stage.

Introduction

In the previous period, the juvenile defendant was treated as an adult defendant during the investigation and trial stages without any regard for his young age as well as his mental and cognitive immaturity. In the face of this injustice and injustice against the latest defendants. Most jurists and legal schools have made great efforts at various local and international levels to remedy injustice against them and treat them fairly and appropriately for their age and mental maturity. This is confirmed by the Iraqi criminal legislator in the Juvenile Protection Act No. 76 of 1983, which includes the specificities of the juvenile accused during the investigation phase.

There is no doubt that the high percentage of crimes committed by juvenile delinquents, in addition to the emergence of dangerous and new patterns of delinquency, have added to the problem of crime new dimensions, which threaten the future of future generations, which constitute the vanguard of society and the source of its human energies. People and money have harmful effects on them and their society at the same time.

Failure to provide guarantees to this group, by protecting and caring for the pervert and re-reforming the deviant and making him an active member, would constitute a serious scourge that threatens the security of society.

This therefore requires that the procedures for prosecution, investigation, trial and execution be compatible with the objective of reform, which means a special judicial organization that hears juvenile cases.

When the crime occurs, the state has a right to punishment that is only by the prosecution before the judiciary, but the prosecution can not be launched from a vacuum but must be built on reasonable grounds, the least of which is the discovery of the crime and the finding of its evidence. This stage is called the stage of inference or collection of evidence.

Then another body, legally empowered, must assess the value of the evidence collected and whether it is sufficient or insufficient to refer the defendant to court and take the appropriate decision to refer it or not, this stage is called the preliminary investigation, which is a middle stage that comes after the evidentiary stage and before the trial stage.

The pre-trial stage is one of the most dangerous stages in the criminal case, and what increases its seriousness is that it represents the first step for the juvenile in the face of public authority

The Important of the study

One of the most important objectives sought by this study is to diagnose the shortcomings in the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Law by providing adequate guarantees for the reform and rehabilitation of the juvenile accused, and identifying the inadequacy of its provisions when applied on the ground.

The objective of the study

Our research aims to show the extent of the application of the provisions of the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Law No. (76) of 1983, as amended. and the guarantees provided for the juvenile. Have the guarantees contained therein been observed?

The problem of the study

The problem of research is an important question:

- Were the guarantees provided by law sufficient to bring justice to juveniles? If the law is not in place to provide these guarantees, is it necessary to pass a new law capable of providing more effective guarantees to this important group?

Research Plan

This research will be divided into two sections according to the following:

The first topic: is guarantees of the accused juvenile in the stage of inference

The second topic: the guarantees of the accused in the procedures followed in the preliminary investigation stage

The first topic

Guarantees of the modern accused at the stage of inference

The legal rules establish a set of guarantees at the evidentiary stage, some of which relate to the formation of agencies dealing with juveniles, and others to the procedures exercised by these agencies in the performance of their duties in prosecuting and arresting juveniles.

There is no doubt that the evidentiary stage is a stage before the initiation of criminal proceedings and is not part of it. As for the juvenile category, it is a police task that raises little controversy after the law entrusted this task to the police under the supervision of the Public Prosecution as its agents. [1].

The importance of this stage lies in the fact that it represents the initial contact with the juvenile and the consequent need to exercise it by specialized bodies in the field of juveniles. International rules, as well as most legislation dealing with juvenile affairs, contain provisions for the formation of a specialized juvenile police. The function of judicial officers other than police officers is limited only by the procedural laws of States and the issue of specialization of judicial officers in juvenile cases, as is the case with police services, is not observed.

This importance is not limited to the specialization of the agencies dealing with juveniles at this stage but also increases in importance to the actions taken by those agencies against juveniles in the exercise of their functions assigned to them by law.

Therefore, we will address in this section the specialization of the juvenile police in Iraqi law in the first requirement, and we address the guarantees of the accused juvenile in the procedures followed in the stage of inference in Iraqi law in the second requirement.

First Requirement

Specialization of the Juvenile Police in Iraqi Law

One of the most important guarantees that legal rules should provide to the category of juvenile delinquents or those at risk of delinquency to devote to the recommendations of the modern criminal policy in the treatment of juveniles is the need to consider their cases at all stages by bodies specialized in juvenile affairs with both preventive and curative objectives.

This modern philosophy focuses on considering that the problem of juvenile delinquency is a social phenomenon that requires prevention and treatment, and the consequent consideration of the psychology and circumstances of juveniles and the realization of their issues in a completely different way from what is followed in the treatment of adults.

To achieve the greatest degree of legal guarantees for juveniles and to preserve their freedoms at the evidentiary stage, it was necessary to create a special and trained police required by the nature of their work, as they represent the beginning of dealing with the juvenile upon arrest, which requires that these elements of the police be at a level of high and deep understanding of the problem of delinquency so that they can form a social relationship between them and the juvenile, and thus play a prominent and effective role in the field of care and prevention [2].

Therefore, we will address the emergence of juvenile police in Iraqi law in the first branch, and then we will address the role of juvenile police in preventing and treating delinquency in the second branch.

Subchapter I: The Emergence of the Juvenile Police in Iraqi Law

The formation of the juvenile police in Iraq [3] went through many stages, and it was the first to recommend the formation of a special police service for juveniles and to provide it with specialized elements (the committee formed under the letter of the presidency of the Republic No. 1133 on 1/12/1971), and the subsequent recommendation of the National Center for Social and Criminal Research in Baghdad in its study on the phenomenon of juvenile homelessness. Indeed, for the first time, a juvenile police station was established in Baghdad Governorate in the Baghdad Governorate Police Directorate on (24/5/1975). The centre was linked to the Directorate of the Judicial Police and began its mission on (27/12/1975) ([4]). Then the rank of the centre was raised to the level of assistant on (4/2/1976) and began its duties on (6/3/1976). In the same year, it was attached to the observation home police station[5]. On 15/1/1981, the Ministry of the Interior issued a

ministerial order No. 841, under which the Juvenile Police Assistant was transformed into a directorate called the Juvenile Police Directorate ([6]).

According to the letter of the Baghdad Governorate Police Directorate No. 17405 dated 15/14/1981, the Juvenile Police Directorate was replaced by the Directorate of Juvenile Police and Social Welfare. In 1983, the Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983 was promulgated. The Directorate of Juvenile Police and Social Welfare was then replaced by the Directorate of Juvenile Police and Social Welfare by the Directorate of Juvenile Police.

Subchapter II: Competence of the Juvenile Police

The traditional police functions of crime prevention and suppression are no longer sufficient to serve the needs of juveniles and address their problem of delinquency. Therefore, the tendency was to single out juveniles with a specialized police service that carries out distinct tasks different from those followed by adults, so the juvenile police must have a role in warding off the danger of delinquency from juveniles, saving them from slipping into the abyss of crime, and providing the means that enable them to pass the delicate stage they are going through in their lives. It also enables them to diagnose the conditions that push them to delinquency or delinquency. Thus, the juvenile police play two basic roles: preventive and curative.

First: Preventive Role

The detection of juvenile delinquency, its place in society, and the elimination of the conditions and factors that encourage it is one of the most important roles exercised by the juvenile police as an administrative control body in the field of juvenile prevention and protection from the risk of delinquency. which are intended to address an underlying social risk of the juvenile's presence in a situation of delinquency, and are intended to protect the juvenile rather than to cause him or her pain. [7].

Police intervention is embodied in its preventive role in organizing and coordinating protection programmes in cooperation with other competent bodies or individually in many and varied ways, the most important of which are [8]:

- 1- Implementing laws that motivate juveniles against corruption.
2. Provide the police with the advice and guidance that the police can provide to parents, schools, workplaces and entertainment, and juveniles themselves.
- 3- Organizing entertainment programs that attract juveniles and occupy their free time ([9]).
- 4- Preventing the presence of juveniles in corrupt places, cafes, theatres, etc.
- 5- Strengthening cooperation with the public and bodies interested in juvenile affairs.

One of the preventive roles of the juvenile police is considered to be the aftercare it performs towards convicted juveniles who have completed treatment programs in the natural environment in which they live, such as helping them return to schools and their workplaces, monitoring them there, and other matters practised by the police that can give a good impression to juveniles, and everything that would consolidate or support the relationship between juveniles and the police, which is no longer only legal but also social. [10].

Second: Therapeutic role

This role is represented in the procedures taken by the police to detect, establish and collect evidence of crimes committed by juveniles or their presence in a situation of delinquency, search and arrest of perpetrators, conduct searches and all necessary to bring juveniles to court and the enforcement of sentences, return to their families, place them in institutions, follow up on their affairs and contact their families, and in general the function of the juvenile police includes the implementation of criminal justice. [11].

Articles 23 and 24 of the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983 define the functions of juvenile police.

It should be noted that the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act has significantly limited the preventive role of the juvenile police, which has many basic tasks other than the above, through its activities to prevent juvenile delinquency, such as monitoring the phenomenon of criminality, monitoring previous persons and preventing them from contacting juveniles, monitoring juveniles' workplaces and intervening appropriately and promptly. The Act neglects the role of the juvenile police in raising awareness, holding seminars on juveniles and guiding them to prevent the risk of delinquency.

Regarding the remedial role of the juvenile police, the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983 entrusts the juvenile police with the task of handing over juveniles immediately upon arrest and bringing them before the investigating judge. In the absence of a juvenile police, the local police shall have the prerogative of the local police. [12].

Second Requirement

Guarantees of the juvenile accused in the procedures followed at the evidentiary stage in Iraqi law

Article 84 of the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983 specifies the procedures to be followed when apprehending a juvenile suspect, namely handing him over immediately upon arrest to the juvenile police in

places where there are juvenile police to be brought before the investigating judge or the juvenile court, expressly indicates that the law, despite its explicit provision for the prompt presentation of a juvenile to the investigating authority and the human rights guarantees that this provides, However, he overlooked the role that the juvenile police can play in dealing with the situation of the juvenile accused, away from judicial procedures that often involve restraining and punishment, or the negative effects that such procedures may have on the psychology and social status of the juvenile.

The issue of restricting the juvenile police, not granting it discretion to act in the situation of the juvenile accused in his best interest, and obliging it in all cases to bring him before the investigating authority, violates one of the fundamental guarantees stipulated in the international rules on the organization of juvenile affairs regarding the avoidance of a juvenile in violation of the Criminal Prosecution Law and to strive as much as possible to live in his social environment, as explained in the previous section. [13].

It should be noted that the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Law, like most legislation on juveniles, omits to develop special provisions regulating the conduct of procedures and including them at this stage. [14]

This was explicitly emphasized by the Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice, when it called for efforts to enact specific national legislation containing a set of rules and provisions specifically applicable to juvenile defendants and to the institutions and bodies entrusted with the administration of juvenile justice, aimed at addressing the diverse needs of juvenile offenders and protecting their fundamental rights and ensuring their full and equitable implementation. [15].

The guarantees enjoyed by the juvenile accused at the stage of evidence collection, which can be inferred from the provisions of the Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23 of 1971, as amended, can be summarized as follows:

Subchapter I: Legality of the means used by the judicial officer when investigating and collecting information:

The legality of the means used by the judicial officer to investigate the crime committed, to identify the perpetrator and to gather the necessary information useful for the investigation is one of the basic guarantees of human rights that the juvenile accused must enjoy at the stage of gathering evidence.

A member of the judicial police shall resort to legitimate means that do not prejudice the freedom and dignity of the human person, and such means shall not in all cases be contrary to the law and public morals.

Article 46 of the Code of Criminal Procedure stipulates that "members of the judicial police shall take all necessary measures to ensure the preservation of the evidence of the crime." However, the aforementioned law does not specify what means a member of the judicial police is entitled to resort to in investigating, collecting and preserving evidence, apprehending the perpetrator and handing it over to the competent authority, but rather refers to the extension of these means to all that the judicial officer deems necessary to carry out his duties stipulated in the law. [16].

Subchapter II - Supervision and Control of the Work of the Judicial Enforcement Member:

A member of the judicial police shall perform his work with all honesty and sincerity and shall avoid anything that may prejudice the integrity of the procedures taken by him while carrying out his duties entrusted to him by law in collecting evidence, in a manner that ensures the protection of the accused, preserves his dignity and avoids any attack that contradicts the principles of human rights.

To achieve this guarantee, a member of the judicial police must be subject to supervision and supervision by a higher authority. This authority was defined in the Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23 of 1971, as amended, where the law subjected the judicial officer to the supervision of the Public Prosecution and the control of the investigating judge and required him to be held legally accountable in the event of his violation. [17].

Hence, we see that the supervision and control of the work of the judicial officer are considered a guarantee of human rights, and protection of the accused from any behaviour that the judicial officer may resort to or use any illegal or immoral means against him that would prejudice the freedoms of persons up to all the evidence of the crime ([18]).

Subchapter III - Writing a report of the procedures carried out by the judicial officer and preserving the evidence of the crime.

Article 41 of the Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23 of 1971, as amended, requires a member of the judicial police to prove all the measures he has taken and to send all the seized information, complaints, minutes and papers to the competent investigating judge immediately.

Recording the procedures carried out by the judicial officer while collecting evidence about the crime committed and preserving its evidence is one of the guarantees of the accused at the stage of editing and collecting evidence, as it preserves his rights from tampering, alteration or forgery, as well as helps in detecting the crime and removing its ambiguity.

The second topic

Guarantees of the juvenile accused in the procedures followed at the preliminary investigation stage In Iraqi law

To ensure the fairness of the actions taken by the competent authorities at this stage, these laws establish a set of legal guarantees that must be available to the parties to the proceedings, especially for the accused, who is the weakest party. The provisions of the Constitution of the Republic of Iraq of 2005 affirm the guarantee and maintenance of the right to litigation^[19], and the fairness of judicial procedures for everyone^[20].

The most important guarantees prescribed to the accused at the stage of preliminary investigation in Iraqi law are as follows:

First Requirement

Safeguards in investigative proceedings

The preliminary investigation stage is a stage after the evidentiary stage, initiated by the investigating authority represented by the investigating judge and the investigator. The legislator has endeavoured to surround this stage with several guarantees that guarantee the accused that their rights, freedoms and the inviolability of their homes are not violated, which are often involved in the procedures undertaken at this stage, such as searches and interrogations. What makes these procedures more dangerous is their misuse by those who carry them out, thus increasing the unlawful violations to which the person of the accused is subjected.

Such violations may result in the risk of punishment of an innocent person through the practice of such unlawful violations. This is therefore one of the most dangerous stages in which the self-determination of the accused passes. Thus, the task of the investigator is primarily aimed at protecting the rights of innocent people and preventing them from falling into indictment rather than at detecting the crime and proving its attribution to the accused, as the accused is innocent until proven guilty. ^[21].

In addition to the foregoing, the guarantees enjoyed by the juvenile accused at the stage of conducting the preliminary investigation, are provided for in the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983 and the Iraqi Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23 of 1971, as amended. We can summarize them as follows:

Subchapter I: Initiating an investigation without confronting a juvenile:

The principle is that the investigation sessions should be public for the parties to the case, and confidential for the public. Laws stipulate this publicity, including the Iraqi Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23 of 1971, as amended^[22].

Although there is an explicit provision on the publicity of the investigation, the law gives the investigating judge the right to make the investigation confidential, even for the litigants, as an exception to the original if there is strong evidence that the investigation proceeds in public creates difficulties for the investigating authority, or helps the accused to obliterate the evidence of the crime, provided that the investigating judge records the reasons that prompted him to make the investigation confidential and that the litigants are allowed to see later the procedures that took place in their absence. ^[23].

The principle of publicity and confidentiality of the investigation in certain cases, adopted by the Iraqi legislature, is generally applied to accused adults and juveniles. ^[24].

The Juvenile Welfare Act introduced a new provision permitting investigations other than confronting a juvenile for crimes against public morals and morals, provided that the person entitled to defend him or her was present in the investigation. The court must inform the juvenile of the action taken against him. ^[25].

The purpose of initiating an investigation without confronting the juvenile is a guarantee that his dignity will not be violated^[26]. And that the repetition of the phrases of the scandalous act should not hurt his psyche (^[27]).

However, article 50 of the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act stipulates that those who have the right to defend the juvenile must attend the investigation. This is one of the guarantees of the juvenile accused during the investigation that enables him to avoid the accusation from himself either by proving the corruption of the evidence of the accusation, or by establishing evidence of its opposite, which is innocence. ^[28].

It is noted from the text of the above article that it makes it mandatory for the presence of the defender, who is often the juvenile's lawyer, in the event of an investigation other than the juvenile's confrontation. But the question that arises here is: is the presence of a lawyer permissible if the investigation is not confidential for the juvenile? And what if the juvenile is unable to secure a lawyer?

This issue has not been addressed by Iraq's Juvenile Welfare Law No. 76 of 1983. However, by referring to the Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23 of 1971, as amended, we note that article 123/b, as amended by Coalition Authority Memorandum No. 7 of 2004, section IV/c, stipulates that a lawyer must be present with the accused at the investigation stage, especially during interrogation, and that the investigation shall not be initiated unless a lawyer is assigned to the accused who does not have a lawyer, and at the expense of the State. The lawyer must be informed of the investigative papers and everything related to the investigation, as confirmed by Article (27) of the Advocacy Law No. (173) of 1965, as amended^[29].

However, article 50 of the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983 lacks an explicit provision for the need to bring the juvenile's guardian or guardian during the investigation.

Section II - Referral of the juvenile to the Office of Personality Study.

Juvenile justice seeks primarily to socially address juvenile delinquency, which can only be done through a thorough knowledge of all his or her circumstances. This exercise of juvenile justice power imposed a focus on the personality of the juvenile and formed the focus of his attention, making the procedures before him characterized by the obligation to conduct social research on the juvenile's situation. and the study of the juvenile's personality, which is called social investigation^[30], assists the juvenile investigating judge to obtain information regarding the personality of the juvenile before him and the influences surrounding him, which enables him to choose the appropriate and most appropriate decision to address the situation of the juvenile (^[31]).

The examination of the situation of juveniles is one of the most important guarantees confirmed by juvenile laws^[32], which the majority of the world's countries have always adopted as a principle for the treatment and reform of juveniles.

Article 51 of the Iraqi legislator adopted this principle in the Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983, stipulating article 51: "First, when a juvenile is charged with a felony and the evidence is sufficient to refer him to the juvenile court, he shall send him to the Personality Study Library;

Therefore, it is clear that the referral of the juvenile to the Personality Study Office takes place in one of two cases:

The first is mandatory, as the investigating judge was obliged to refer the juvenile accused of a felony, and the evidence was sufficient to refer him to the juvenile court, to the Personality Study Office.

Second: permissibility if the crime of which the juvenile is accused is a misdemeanour, and the evidence is sufficient to refer him to the juvenile court, and the circumstances of the case or the juvenile's situation so require.

However, what is the case with the offences committed by the juvenile, which indicate psychological deviations or complexes that require studying the situation of the juvenile and conducting a social investigation with him?

The Iraqi legislator's tendency is not to refer a juvenile accused of an offence to the Personality Study Office, as evidenced by the text of Article 51 of the Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983.

To achieve the desired objective of the Juvenile Welfare Act, as a preventive and curative law that seeks to protect juveniles from delinquency and to take appropriate measures to deal with delinquency, we believe that the legislator should intervene to give the examining magistrate discretion to refer the accused to the Personality Study Office, regardless of the gravity of the crime committed. But this must be done according to his conviction and the circumstances and circumstances of each case. The legislator must also seriously intervene to ensure the effective application of legal texts by imposing some kind of control over the workers in the personality study offices.^[33]

Section III - Guarantees of the juvenile accused against the decisions of the investigating judge.

After the completion of the investigation procedures by the investigating authority, the competent referral authority (which may be the same as the investigating authority as applicable in Iraqi legislation, and may be an independent authority competent for referral other than the authority that carried out the investigation) (^[34]), decides to refer the juvenile accused to the juvenile court if the act attributed to him is punishable and the evidence is sufficient to prosecute him. To preserve the integrity of the body of the accused, he must be informed of the necessary safeguards, including:

A- Rejection of the complaint and closure of the investigation:

If the investigating judge finds that the act committed is not punishable by law, that the complainant has waived his complaint and that the crime is permissible without the judge's consent, or if the accused is not legally responsible due to his young age, the judge shall issue a decision to reject the complaint and close the case permanently.^[35]

However, what is blamed on the Iraqi legislature is that it does not take into account the view of some sophisticated legislation, such as the United States legislation, which grants the investigative authority the right to transfer some minor cases to social institutions to address the individual situation in a manner that suits the interest of the juvenile and society. This policy has been known as the policy of non-criminal intervention (^[36]). This tolerant attitude is perhaps the meaning of rule 11.2 of the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Administration of Juvenile Justice (the Beijing Rules), which empowers the police, prosecutors, or other bodies dealing with juvenile cases, to adjudicate such cases at their discretion without the need for court hearings.

The failure to give the investigating judge the authority to act on the status of a juvenile defendant contradicts the objectives of the Juvenile Welfare Act to exclude the juvenile as much as possible from criminal prosecution and to give preference to the therapeutic aspect over the injunctive and punishment aspect. If the investigating judge does not have this power, what is the point of referring the juvenile to the Personality Study Office, which is provided for in the Juvenile Welfare Act, and is considered one of the basic and distinct rules at the stage of the preliminary investigation, for which the legislator commends him.

(a) The juvenile's case must be separated from adult defendants and referred to the competent court:

The Juvenile Welfare Act requires that when the juvenile accused is referred to adult defendants, the juvenile case must be cassation and referred to the competent court[1].

This was confirmed by the Court of Cassation in one of its decisions, which stated: "If the Criminal Court finds that one of the defendants referred to it is a juvenile, it shall disperse the case in respect of the juvenile defendant and refer it to the Juvenile Court for trial before it on the charge against him."

(b) Reasoning the decisions of the investigating judge and informing the Public Prosecution thereof:

The reasoning of the investigating judge's decision is a sure guarantee for the accused, whether juvenile or adult, to appeal the judge's decision, either by himself or by the Public Prosecution. Although the Iraqi legislature did not refer to this explicitly, it made it one of the data to be included in the referral decision[3], although it would be preferable to stipulate that the decision of the investigating judge should be expressly reasoned.

The Public Prosecution shall also be informed of the investigating judge's decision. It is also a guarantee for the accused to scrutinize the decision of the investigating judge ([4]).

Second Requirement**Guarantees of the juvenile accused in arrest and detention**

Perhaps the arrest of the accused, as an investigative procedure, is no less important than other investigative procedures such as interrogation, search, etc. Rather, it represents the most serious of these measures, because it violates the freedom and dignity of the human person, which is one of his most precious rights, and because it contradicts the most important principles of criminal science, which restrict that the accused is innocent until proven guilty.

The individual has the right to personal liberty, and at the same time governmental authorities may intervene if it is established that such personal liberty threatens the security of society and the country. [5].

It is clear from the foregoing that the principle is that a person may not be deprived of his liberty and that the exception is the permissibility of restricting or arresting a person on legal grounds or, if certain cases exist, in the implementation of a judicial order. However, this statement does not work when the person concerned is a juvenile, with its specificity that must be taken into account when restricting his liberty. Therefore, the legislator singled out the restriction of the juvenile's liberty with certain guarantees that differ from those followed by adult defendants, which can be summarized as follows:

Section I. Guarantees of the juvenile accused upon arrest.

Arrest means "the arrest of the accused by the person charged with his arrest and placing him at his disposal for a short period until he is brought before the investigating authority or the body that issued the order to act on him". [6].

Thus, the arrest is considered one of the serious measures resorted to by the examining magistrate at the preliminary investigation stage, since it violates the personal freedom of the accused.

Concerning the provisions of the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983, article 48 of the Act stipulates that: "Upon arrest, a juvenile shall be handed over to the juvenile police in places where there is a juvenile police to be brought before the investigating judge or the juvenile court."

However, the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act did not regulate the arrest of juvenile suspects at the initial investigation stage, as is the case with most juvenile laws[7], which constitutes an acute deficiency that must be avoided.

Similarly, we did not find in the Juvenile Welfare Act a provision specifying a period that must be observed during the period of arrest. However, concerning the provisions of the Iraqi Constitution of 2005, we find that it sets a period not exceeding 24 hours from the time of the arrest of the accused to be presented to the competent investigating judge to decide on his subject, provided that it may not be extended except once and for the same period.

One of the guarantees enjoyed by the accused in general during his arrest, as stipulated in the Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23 of 1971 (as amended), is that the arrest warrant is issued by a competent judicial authority and in cases where the law permits it. [8].

Section II - Guarantees of the juvenile accused upon arrest.

Criminal proceedings may sometimes require the arrest of the juvenile, whether for the proper investigation, to prevent his escape, to protect him from continuing his deviant behaviour, or from being subjected to reprisals from the victim's family. Detention itself is an exceptional measure, as it violates personal freedom, which is a fundamental right of citizens. It can constitute a violation thereof, whether arbitrary or legally unjustified.

In addition to restricting his freedom, it deprives him of parental affection, isolates him from his natural environment, and causes him psychological trauma that may continue with him until all subsequent judicial proceedings, becoming in his view an extension of the coercive measure of deprivation of liberty taken against him ([9]).

Based on the foregoing, the Iraqi legislator has taken into account this specificity of juveniles when they are arrested. This specificity is manifested in the following:

(a) Determination of juvenile arrests:

The Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983 specifies the cases in which a juvenile may not be arrested, the cases in which a juvenile can be arrested, and the cases in which he must be arrested. [10].

The Act permits the arrest of a juvenile if the offence of which he is accused is a felony or misdemeanour, and if the purpose of his arrest is to examine him or study his personality. [11] The law also permits the arrest of a juvenile when there is no guarantor for him.

The law requires the arrest of a juvenile if he is accused of a felony punishable by death if he is over fourteen years of age.

However, the question that can be raised in this regard is if the juvenile is accused of a felony punishable by death and does not exceed the age of fourteen: is his arrest mandatory or permissible?

It is clear from the concept of violation ([12]) in the interpretation of the text of Article (52) of the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Law No. (76) of 1983, and since the interpretation aims to reveal the intention of the legislator, which can give the text, in the end, its sound meaning and not contradictory with the interest or right to be protected nor with the legal system in which it operates, which is, in the end, the meaning that expresses the intention of the legislator ([13]). It can be said that if the juvenile is not more than fourteen years of age, the arrest shall be permissible.

However, the Iraqi legislature is guilty of permitting the arrest of a juvenile without specifying a specific age at which he must be arrested. This is understood from the text of Article (52) referred to above, which is absolute ([14]).

(b) Determining a place of detention for the juvenile:

The privacy of the juvenile has imposed the allocation of a place for the detention of the juvenile, which is far from the situation concerning the detention of adults, which is a sure guarantee that this privacy will be observed and that he will not mix with detainees of the age of majority.

The Iraqi legislature followed this approach when it made the place of detention of a juvenile in the observation home, and in places where there is no observation home, the law required measures to be taken to prevent the mixing of the juvenile with other adult detainees. [15].

It should be noted that the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983 does not specify a period of detention for juveniles, which means referring to the general rules contained in the Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23 of 1971 (as amended) ([16]), which apply to adult and juvenile defendants ([17]). This is based on the provisions of article 108 of the Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983, which provides for reference to the provisions of the Penal Code and the Code of Criminal Procedure in respect of what is not provided for in this Act by the nature, objectives and foundations of the Juvenile Welfare Act.

However, the privacy of juveniles dictates that juveniles should not be treated as adults when arrested. It should be noted that the Juvenile Welfare Act No. 64 of 1972, repealed, deals with the duration of juvenile detention and the maximum period of detention for a juvenile, article 14 of which stipulates that the period of detention shall not exceed 45 days.

Therefore, we can say that if a juvenile is arrested, he must enjoy all the rights and guarantees stipulated in international human rights norms, especially those related to the treatment of detainees and convicted persons. Juveniles must be protected and cared for, and all social, educational, professional, psychological, medical and physical services must be provided, taking into account age, sex and personality.

Conclusion

A society that develops plans and strategies for reform in all aspects of its life, especially those related to justice in general, criminal justice in particular, and those related to juveniles in particular, is a society that is keen on continuity, stability and ensuring progress and well-being for its members. This explains the progress of Western societies in many aspects of life, as they realized this early, developed various strategies to achieve it, and applied them on the ground, especially if we realize that today's event is the man of the future.

The study showed that the problem of juvenile delinquency is one of the serious problems that has emerged at the international and domestic levels and has become a concern of the United Nations in the field of combating crime.

International conventions work to support criminal justice for juveniles by providing all the elements of a fair and fair trial, including formations and procedures, and surrounding it with a solid fence of guarantees that ensure its realization.

The Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983 continues to reflect this trend. He has included in his texts the basic concepts based on the adoption of a compassionate and compassionate humanistic view of juveniles, aimed at reform and rehabilitation. This trend is commendable, respected and appreciated, but it does not achieve its intended purpose and does not reach the objectives of discriminating juveniles and giving them treatment differently from adults, by adding more guarantees for juvenile delinquents or delinquents and homeless persons.

Results

The Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act provides for the existence of a juvenile investigating judge (art. 49) and a juvenile court presided over by a judge and two members, one a jurist and the other a juvenile scientist. They are regulated in felonies. Misdemeanours are dealt with by the juvenile court judge (art. 56), but the law does not extend jurisdiction in this way, since Article 49 states that in the absence of a juvenile investigating judge, the ordinary investigating judge shall do so. Article 57 thereof also states that In the absence of a juvenile court for misdemeanours and offences, the matter shall be up to the ordinary misdemeanour judge.

2. There is nothing in the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act that indicates that a lawyer must be present with the juvenile. Article 60 provides for the possibility of a juvenile's guardian, a relative or a representative of social institutions to defend a juvenile.

3. There is no explicit provision in the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act that obliges the court to immediately inform the juvenile's family of what is attributed to him.

4. Similarly, there is no explicit provision in the Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act to enable juveniles to express their opinion on charges against them.

5. The presence of the social representative during investigation and trial proceedings is not generalized in Iraqi legislation, so we find that Article 21 of the Iraqi law requires the investigating judge to refer the juvenile to the Office of Personality Study in felonies only before referring him to court. In misdemeanours, this is not obligatory and remains subject to the judge's scrutiny, and the juvenile court is not obliged in misdemeanour cases to send the juvenile to the Personality Study Office unless it deems that his circumstances so require (Article 61/ iii). The presence of the representative of the Personality Study Office is required at the trial hearings in cases in which his representative submits a report (Article 61).

6. Article 71 of the Juvenile Welfare Act sets out the authority competent to hear appeals against judgements, and two periods are specified, the first of which is 15 days in the case of a felony sentence.

Recommendations

At the end of our study, we can make the following recommendations:

1- It is necessary to give great importance to the legal drafting of texts, and to take note of the content and concept of the text before drafting it, and the consequent need for the wording of the text to be extremely accurate and clearly express its content and purpose, and this means trying to move away from drafting texts in a way that reveals ambiguity, surrounded by doubt, and opens the doors of diligence in shortening them.

2- The need to address the provisions contained in the Juvenile Welfare Act in a manner consistent with the specificity of the Juvenile Welfare Act and the segment for which it is intended, namely the juvenile segment, and to support it with new texts that fill the deficiency in it, making it an integrated law that covers aspects of dealing with juveniles in form and content, or to legislate a law of judicial procedures for juveniles, which takes into account the best interest of the juvenile throughout juvenile proceedings and avoids referring to the general rules of the Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23. of 1931 and the Penal Code No. 111 of 1969 (as amended).

3. Make the presence of the lawyer with the juvenile a duty at all stages of the proceedings, regardless of the criminal description attributed to the juvenile.

4. The Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act must include a general provision affirming that the detention of a juvenile cannot be resorted to except on an exceptional basis, in case of extreme necessity, and for the shortest possible period, provided that this does not conflict with the best interests of the juvenile, and the creation of a series of alternative non-custodial measures that may replace detention, as well as determining the maximum period of such detention in line with the status and age of the juvenile.

5. Grant the greatest possible discretionary powers to those working in charge of juvenile justice affairs to act in the juvenile's best interests at all stages, from police units to the preliminary investigation to the trial stage, taking into account the exercise of effective control over the authorities to ensure the proper application of the guarantees granted to the juvenile.

6. The measures to be adopted must be determined based on the circumstances of the juvenile and the reasons for his behaviour, and the adoption of the age group or type of offence as a criterion for determining the measure must be avoided.

References

Ibrahim Al-Mashahi, Al-Mukhtar from the Court of Cassation, Criminal Section, Part III, Al-Zaman Press, Baghdad, 1997, p. 805.

Ibrahim HarbMuhaisen, Police Responsibility in Dealing with Delinquency, Homelessness and Crime, a research submitted to the sixth scientific symposium entitled (Youth Problems in Contemporary Arab Society) held at the Arab Center for Security Studies and Training, Riyadh, for the period (2-6/11/1985), p. 41.

Ahmed Abdul Karim Al-Maini, Guarantees of the Accused in the Pre-Trial Stage in Iraqi Legislation, pp. (9-11). Research published in the Journal of Legislation and the Judiciary. On the following website: <http://tqmag.net/body>.

- BaraaMunther Abdul Latif, Criminal Policy in the Juvenile Welfare Law (A Comparative Study), Dar Al-Hamid for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, 2009, p. 88.
- Hassan Sadiq Al-Marsafawi, Principles of Criminal Procedure, Al-Maaref Foundation, Alexandria, 1982, p. 348.
- Hassan OdehZaal, Fair Trial Guarantees in Iraqi Legislation, research published on the following website: <http://www.fcdrs.com>.
- The Iraqi Constitution of 2005
- Ralph Riachi, A Comparative Study on Juvenile Justice in Some Arab Countries (Jordan, Algeria, Iraq, Lebanon, Egypt, Morocco, Yemen), without place and date of publication, p. 71.
- Suzanne KarimRazouki, Investigation and Trial Procedures in Juvenile Cases. It is a research paper submitted as part of the graduation requirements from the Judicial Institute, Baghdad, 2007-2008, p. 26.
- ShaimaNaimHuwain, Guarantees of the Juvenile Accused in the Investigation and Trial Stage, a research presented as part of the study requirements for the second stage at the Judicial Institute, Baghdad, 2011, p. 44.
- TahaZahran, Criminal Juvenile Treatment, PhD thesis discussed at the Faculty of Law at Cairo University, 1978, pp. 266-267.
- The phenomenon of Hamza Salman, procedures and measures prescribed in the Juvenile Welfare Law. It is a research submitted to the Judicial Institute as part of the requirements of higher specialized studies (criminal section), Baghdad, 1685, p. 46.
- Iraqi Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23 of 1971, as amended.
- Iraqi Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23 of 1971 (as amended)
- Iraqi Code of Criminal Procedure No. 23 of 1971.
- Iraqi Juvenile Welfare Act No. 76 of 1983, as amended.
- Kazem Abdullah Hussein Al-Shammari, Interpretation of Penal Texts (A Comparative Study of Islamic Jurisprudence), PhD thesis submitted to the College of Law at the University of Baghdad, 2001, pp. 393-394.
- Maher SabriKazim, Human Rights, Democracy and Public Freedoms, Al-Kitab Press, Baghdad, 2010, p. 89.
- Mohammed Rashid Al-Omar , The Origins of Criminal Investigation in Islamic Law, Dar Al-Nawader, Beirut, Lebanon, 2008, p. 349.
- Mahmoud Al-Sibai, The Role of the Police in Combating Crime. Proceedings of the first anti-crime workshop in the United Arab Republic. Publications of the National Center for Social and Criminal Research, Cairo, 1961, p. 276.
- Mustafa Ibrahim Al-Zalmi, Usul al-Fiqh fi al-Textile, vol. 2, Cairo, Legal Library, Baghdad, 2002, p. 436.
- MuftahBouBakr Al-Matradi, Adaptation of Criminal Procedures to Juvenile Crime (A Comparative Study), Alexandria University, Faculty of Law, 1997, p. 266.
- Henri Velge, Les Tribunaux pour enfants, Etablissements Emile Bruylant, Bruxelles, 1972, p. 27.

Author Information

Dr. Muna Asree Hamad
Dijlah University College
